

Prediction of Breast Cancer, Comparative Study of Machine Learning Techniques Using WEKA Tool

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Abstract-Breast most cancers is a 2nd most important reason of cancer death in women after lung most cancers. Breast cancer takes place when boom of a few breast tissues and it is able to arise in any part of the Breast. it is able to be averted if the treatment is began at the early degree of the Breast most cancers. There are numerous types of breast cancer, and many specific methods to explain them. Breast cancer is a malignant tumor i.e., a group of cancer tissues springing up from the cells of the breast. Its remedy relies upon on the degree of most cancers. It may consist of chemotherapy, radiation, hormone therapy and surgery. This paper compares the output of various machine learning techniques like Simple k-means, Canopy, Hierarchical Clustering on breast cancer dataset.

Keywords-Machine Learning, Breast Cancer, Simple K-Means, Hierarchical Clustering, Canopy, Weka, Accuracy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer develops due to out-of-control cellular boom which can unfold to other components of the frame. Different forms of cancer exist, with breast cancer being the most often diagnosed most cancers in women. it's also the second maximum common reason of most cancers death in women[2]. when cells in the breast start to develop out of control, breast cancer develops. Normally, these cells form a tumor. Early detection and diagnosis can help to reduce mortality rates to a greater degree.

Breast most cancers is one of the maximum deadly and heterogeneous disease on this present generation that reasons the death of considerable

wide variety of girls all around the global [1].

A large number of fatty and fibrous tissues in the breast begin to develop abnormally, which leads to breast cancer. Cancer cells grow across tumors, resulting in various stages of many forms of breast cancer that develop when cells and tissues in the breast become infected and spread across the body[3]. There are distinct varieties of breast most cancers which takes place while affected cells and tissues spread all through the body.

The primary test for breast cancer is mammography. If anomalies are found, hints for the subsequent level of analysis are made. nice Needle Aspiration (FNA) is a sort of biopsy that is recommended if abnormalities have been located after the mammography. in this take a look at, we are the use of the results of FNA for prediction motive, that is received from various datasets Prediction is a form of facts analysis this is used to expect future records trends. With the present-day technology, the prediction and prognosis of cancer are possible.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

K Shailaja⁴, B. Seetharamulu⁴, M. A. Jabbar⁴ makes use of the okay nearest neighbor (KNN) (KNN) algorithm for class of breast most cancers tumors as benign and malignant. it is applied the use of the R tool. The dataset used within the take a look at is the Wisconsin Breast cancer (unique) Dataset (WBCD) from UCI machine learning

repository.

Samiksha Mame¹, Shwetna Churi¹, Maheshwarya Mame¹ makes use of algorithms particularly k-method and choice trees to predict Breast cancer Cells in the human body with the aid of using massive datasets available.

Noreen Fahima², Li Liu², Sha Hong², Haroon Ahmed² are gives the comparative evaluation of device gaining knowledge of, deep gaining knowledge of and records mining techniques getting used for the prediction of breast most cancers. Many researchers have positioned their efforts on breast most cancers diagnoses and prognoses, each technique has awesome accuracy price and it varies for unique conditions, device and datasets being used.

Prateek P. Sengar³, Mihir J. Gaikwad³, Prof. Ashlesha S. Nagdive³ 2 machine Learning to know algorithms is proposed to evaluate specifically Logistic Regression and choice Tree set of rules on the Wisconsin (Diagnostic) information Set and use the algorithm with the first-rate accuracy for predicting Breast most cancers.

III. METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to Predict Breast Cancer into two categories (absence and presence) using machine learning techniques[1]. This phase gives the class method used to are expecting the Breast most cancers primarily based on the behavioral functions[3]. The one-of-a-kind traits are mean_radius, mean_texture, mean_perimeter, mean_area, mean_smoothness and diagnosis. The technique includes 3 critical levels, which might be amassing dataset, pre-processing and classification as shown in figure 1.

A. WEKA

It is an open source software that includes tools for data pre-processing, machine learning algorithm

implementation, and visualization tools, allowing you to create gadget mastering techniques and observe them to actual-international facts mining issues[4]. WEKA implements some of algorithms in each of these categories. You can choose an algorithm and set the preferred parameters and run it on the dataset[4]. Then, WEKA might provide you with the statistical output of the version processing. The diverse models can be implemented at the same dataset[4]. you could then examine the outputs of various fashions and select the high-quality that meets your reason.

As a result, the usage of WEKA outcomes in a faster improvement of system getting to know fashions at the complete[4].

B. Collecting Dataset

A number of variables are used to classify whether a person has a chance for presence or absence of breast cancer. The dataset used in this study comes from the Kaggle repository, and it contains 569 instances of Breast Cancer with 6 attributes and a known target class. This data set is used as training data for the classifier.

Figure1: Methodology for Breast Cancer Classification

C. Pre-Processing

In data mining, pre-processing is a crucial stage. It deals with entries that are missing, incomplete, or invalid for a variety of motives, including facts

entry errors. In addition, there also are attributes that aren't relevant to the research in statistics mining[3]. The irrelevant information such as id must additionally be eliminated from the dataset due to the fact its presence can reduce the satisfactory or accuracy of the information mining class experiment[3]. The dataset for this study is made up of nominal values. These data must be turned into numerical values, which means the nominal values should be transformed into numerical values[3]. With the aid of transforming the nominal into numerical values, the records are actually able to fed into class algorithm[3].

D. Clustering Experiment

The clustering experiment is completed the use of Waikato surroundings for understanding evaluation (WEKA).

In this paper, we will use different machine learning algorithms and techniques for Breast Cancer Prediction such as Simple KMeans, Canopy and Hierarchical Clustering to compare the results to see which algorithm has the best accuracy for the proper prediction of presence or absence of Breast Cancer.

E. Evaluation Matrix

An evaluation matrix is necessary for evaluating the effects of a type experiment[3]. The aim is to create a unmarried measurement that can be used across multiple classification methods so that results can be compared [3]. On this work, the evaluation metrics used includes the clustering accuracy and time taken to build the model.

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

In this study, we will use different machine learning algorithms and techniques for Breast Cancer and are listed below:

A. Clustering Algorithms

Simple K-Means: K-means Clustering is an

unmanaged getting to know algorithm this is used to remedy the clustering issues in machine studying or facts technology. k-means clustering is a way of vector quantization, initially from signal processing, that goals to partition n observations into ok clusters wherein each remark belongs to the cluster with the nearest imply, serving as a prototype of the cluster[1].

Figure2: Classification Accuracy by Simple K-Means

Canopy: Canopy Clustering is regularly used as a preliminary step in greater rigorous clustering strategies, together with okay-means Clustering[1]. The canopy clustering algorithm is an unmonitored pre-clustering. it's miles regularly used as preprocessing step for the okay-approach algorithm or the Hierarchical clustering set of rules.. Its miles intended to speed up clustering operations on huge records units, in which the use of any other algorithm at once may be impractical due to the size of the information set.

```
Canopy clustering
=====

Number of canopies (cluster centers) found: 3
T2 radius: 0.788
T1 radius: 0.964

Cluster 0: 12.146524,17.914762,78.075406,462.790196,0.092478,1, [357] <0>
Cluster 1: 18.467176,21.926706,122.110176,1082.397647,0.101547,0, [170] <1,2>
Cluster 2: 13.397619,20.302381,88.065,557.338095,0.108368,0, [42] <1,2>

Time taken to build model (full training data) : 0.22 seconds

=== Model and evaluation on training set ===

Clustered Instances

0      357 ( 63%)
1      134 ( 24%)
2       78 ( 14%)
```

Figure3: Classification Accuracy by Canopy

Hierarchical Clustering: Hierarchical clustering, additionally called hierarchical cluster analysis, is an algorithm that companies similar gadgets into groups referred to as clusters. The endpoint is a set of clusters, in which every cluster is distinct from each other cluster, and the gadgets inside each cluster are extensively much like every other. inside the k-means cluster analysis educational I provided a strong creation to one of the most popular clustering strategies.

```
=== Clustering model (full training set) ===

Cluster 0
(0.0:0.21605,|||||)

Cluster 1
|||||

Time taken to build model (full training data) : 4.89 seconds

=== Model and evaluation on training set ===

Clustered Instances

0      212 ( 37%)
1      357 ( 63%)
```

Figure4: Classification Accuracy by Hierarchical Clustering

V. RESULT

The clustering of this dataset was done by predicting between presence and absence of Breast Cancer based on their behavioral features. The dataset had a total of 6 nominal attributes (features). Result of the testing using evaluation on the training dataset indicate that Simple KMeans has same accuracy level to Hierarchical when compares to Canopy. However, the Simple KMeans method is faster than Hierarchical and Canopy in terms of processing speed. Below Table1 shows the performance comparison chart of four algorithms on Breast cancer dataset.

ML Techniques	Time Taken to Build a Model
Simple KMeans	0.71s
Canopy	0.22s
Hierarchical Clustering	4.89s

Table 1: Performance Comparison Chart

VI.CONCLUSION

Prediction of Breast Cancer is very important, because prediction helps in the prevention and diagnosis of the disease. It is so critical to correctly predict the presence and absence of breast cancer before disease getting worst. Here we consider Breast Cancer dataset from Kaggle repository and applied different machine learning techniques to predict the presence and absence of Breast Cancer. This paper supplied the methodology and effects for Breast cancer Prediction experiment primarily based on their behavioral functions. This comparison study has given us a better understanding of how the various machine learning models work and how they perform in real-world scenarios.

VII. FUTURE WORK

In data mining, we know that as the size of training dataset increases, the performance of the created model would be enhanced. As a future work, we can also include other attributes like color change, pain etc. and more records that are collected as part of research and apply different machine learning techniques on the new dataset. This will result in improving the model accuracy of the training dataset which is used.

VIII. REFERENCES

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